

Effect of suicide rates on life expectancy

Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

Data

I will collect data using the portal Kaggle.com. The experiment will use two datasets - [WHO Suicide Statistics](#) and [WHO Life Expectancy](#). Both datasets are in the simple format csv and are free to use under the license Creative Commons Attribution-NoNCommercial-ShareALike 3.0 IGO.

The WHO Suicide Statistics dataset has 43 776 records and 6 variables: **country**, which is of type string and have 141 unique values, **year**, which is of type string and has a range between 1979 and 2017, **sex**, which is type of string and has 2 unique values, **age**, which is type of string and has 6 categories, **suicides_no**, which is type of integer and is number of suicides, and **population**, which is type of integer. The whole size of dataset is 1,77 MB.

The WHO Life Expectancy dataset has 2 938 rows and 22 variables: **country**, which is of type string and have 141 unique values, **year**, which is of type integer and has a range between 2000 and 2015, **status**, which is type of string, has two categories and indicates if the country has developed or developing status, **life expectancy**, which is type of float and indicates number of life expectancy in age, **adult mortality**, which is type of integer and indicates adult mortality rates of both sexes, that means probably of dying between 15 and 60 year per 1000 population, **infant deaths**, which is type of integer and indicates number of infant deaths per 1000 population, **alcohol**, which is type of float and indicates alcohol recorded per capita (15+) consumption in litres of pure alcohol, **percentage expenditure**, which is type of float and indicates expenditure on health as a percentage of Gross Domestic Product per capita, **hepatitis B**, which is type of integer and indicates Hepatitis B immunization coverage among 1-year-olds, **measles**, which is type of integer and indicates number of reported measles per 1000 population, **BMI**, which is type of float and indicates average boddy mass index of entire population, **under-five deaths**, which is type of integer and indicates number of under-five deaths per 1000 population, **polio**, which is type of integer and indicates polio immunization coverage among 1-year-old in percent, **total expenditure**, which is type of float and indicates general government expenditure on healtg as a percatage of total government expenditure, **diphtheria**, which is type of integer and indicates diphtheria tetanus toxoid and pertussis (DTP3) immunization coverage among 1-year-olds, **HIV/AIDS**, which is type of float and indicates deaths per 1 000 live births HIV/AIDS (0-4 years), **GDP**, which is type of float and indicates Gross Domestic Product per capita in USD, **population**, which is type of integer and indicates population of the country, **thinness 1-19 years**, which is type of float and indicates prevalence of thinness among children and adolescents for age 10 to 19, **thinness 5-9 years**, which is type of float and indicates prevalence of thinness among children for age 5 to 9, **income composition of resources**, which is type of float and indicates Human Development Index in terms of income composition of resources in the range 0 and 1, and **schooling**, which is type of float and indicates number of years of schooling in years. The whole size of dataset is 325.63 KB.

I will clean, preprocess and merge the datasets by year and country and use these 13 variables: Country, Year, Suicides number, Life expectancy, Adult Mortality, Infant deaths, Alcohol, Under-five deaths, HIV/AIDS, GDP, Population, Income composition of resources

and Schooling. The final dataset will have around 1 400 rows because of missing values in some rows. The data will be exported to csv file with comma separator and file size will be around 100 KB.

Since the final file will be in csv format and will be about 100 KB in size, it will be possible to save it on long-term storage such as Zenodo, but also on github. I decided to use the csv format because my default data also uses the csv format and because the data is easier to read and can be opened in a simple text editor. Long-term data on year, country, number of suicides and life expectancy should be retained. The final file will be uploaded to the [github](#) as well as on [Zenodo](#).

Source

I will use Python 3.7.9, numpy 1.20.1, pandas 1.2.3 JupyterLab notebook for data processing and for experiment as well. Moreover, I will use seaborn 0.11.1, matplotlib 3.4.1, statsmodels 0.12.2, scikit-learn 0.24.1 for the experiment. I will create two JupyterLab notebooks: one for preprocessing and one for the experiment. I will write code into these notebooks. The final code will be uploaded to the [github](#) as well as on [Zenodo](#).

How will the data be collected or created?

The project will be divided into 4 folders using a pattern - [SERIAL_NUMBER]0_[DESCRIPTION] - for data, code, output, documents: 10_Data, 20_Code, 30_Output, 40_Documents. All files in the folders will use a pattern - [SERIAL_NUMBER]0_[DESCRIPTION]_[VERSION]_[ADDITION INFORMATION].[SUFFIX], for instance, 10_life_expectancy_v00_orig.csv for original dataset of life expectancy. The project will have 3 special files - LICENSE.md for a description of the license, README.md for a basic introduction with the project and requirements.txt, where will be mentioned all libraries requirements. Versioning will be handled by special naming of the file and using the Github repository. I will also use versioning provided by Zenodo in the format X.X.X.

Data

The data will be created during the preprocessing. As a first step, I will start with the WHO Life Expectancy dataset. After loading data into pandas dataset, firstly, I will select wanted variables - country, year, life expectancy, adult mortality, infant deaths, alcohol, under-five deaths, HIV/AIDS, GDP, population, income composition of resources and schooling. Then, I will retype the variable year from Integere to String and set Country and Year as index. Then, I will check data by the functions such as head and dtypes and save the dataset as csv to the folder 10_Data named 10_life_expectancy_v01_clean.csv. As a second step, I will select following variables country, year, suicides number and population from the loaded second dataset WHO Suicide Statistics and I will rename the variable suicides_no to Suicides number and population to population2. I will also retype the variable year from Integere to String and set Country and Year as index. Then, I will drop all rows, where the values in the column suicides number are missing and group them by year and country. Then, I will check data by the functions such as head and dtypes and save the dataset as csv to the folder 10_Data named 20_suicide_rates_v01_clean.csv.

As a last step, I will merge these two datasets by index - country and year. Then I will clean missing data: I will unify two population variables, for life expectancy I will delete all rows with missing values and for remaining variables I will add values using the function fill, which fill the values according to the previous row. After all, I will save the merged dataset as csv to the folder 10_Data named 30_merged_dataset_v00_final.csv.

Source

The source code will be create as two JupyterLab notebooks, one for preprocessing named 10_preprocessing.ipynb, where will be implement the previously mentioned procedure, and one named 20_experiment.ipynb. In the second notebook there will be implemented the experiment, where I will start with loading the final dataset. Then I will create a second dataset which will be scaled by the min-max normalization.

Firstly, I will describe the non-scaled dataset to get deeper insight into the data and check data quality, then I will display a correlation among all columns and filter more interested variables into the issue with two main variables suicides number, life expectancy and correlate a second time. After correlation, I will also display a pairplot of filtered variables and will look for the patterns. After these operations, I will lay down a hypothesis, which I will try to prove using a simple regression only between suicides number and life expectancy. Finally, I will save all figures and the final regression output to the folder 30_Output.

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Data and source code will be stored on the Zenodo portal, for long-term storage. Source code will contain whole GitHub code with data, output and documents as well. The document folder will contain summary of the whole experiment with basic description of data, source code, results and the experiment diagram. I will also comment the source code and write the readme file of project, where will be abstract of the experiment, license, used technologies and how to run the experiment.

Finally, I will fill all possible metadata provided by Zenodo, which are: publication date, title, authors, description, where will be mentioned the abstract of the project, basic data description and license, version, language, keywords, license and contact person with ORCID. Zenodo will automatically create DOI.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

Both datasets were collected by WHO and united nations website and contain data for a specific country in a given year. Therefore, the data are already anonymized in this way and it is not possible to identify any person, as the data always counts on the entire population. The data is shared with the license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO, therefore, I can use datasets in a non-commercial way and I can make derivatives of them if I state my source, which I will do. Under the same license, I will share my final data and source code as well.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

Both datasets were collected by WHO and united nations website under the license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO, therefore, I can use datasets in a non-commercial way and I can make derivatives of them if I state my source, which I will do. Under the same license, I will share my final data and source code as well.

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

All data size is within kilobytes, so I can use the Github repository, where I will use the free version, as well as on my laptop to back up the whole experiment. No additional fees will be required. In addition, individual datasets will be versioned. Data will be backed up only a few times because of their simplicity. I will be responsible for data and source recovery. In case of an event of an incident, I will restore the data from the git repository. Metadata will be created directly on the Zenodo repository. The project does not contain any sensitive data.

How will you manage access and security?

The project does not contain any sensitive data. Access to the project will be controlled using the GitHub repository. The repository will be publicly available with all data and source.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

All data and source will be stored for a long time, because there are no legal and regulatory purposes above them and on the Zenodo portal, which are stored safely for the future in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists. The data and code source can be used to research suicide prevention. The data can be easily used thanks to the csv format and description in many cases.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

All data and source will be stored on the Zenodo portal, which are stored safely for the

future in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists. The portal is completely free. Preparing data for sharing and storage took a few hours.

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

Data and code source will be shared on the Zenodo and Github portals. Users will find out about the project through these two portals and also through the university. All data will be shared without any restrictions under the license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO. Both the data and the code will have a persistent identifier. I will make my data available 15.4.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

All data are under the license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO and therefore I can no longer minimize the restrictions. Data are needed exclusively for the months of March and April 2021 due to ongoing assignment at the university. I don't expect any data sharing issues.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

Since this project is carried out by an individual, all responsibility falls on him. This applies to the implementation of the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised, as well as data management activity. The individual will be responsible for all activities data capture, metadata production, data quality, storage and backup, data archiving & data sharing, as well as ensuring that data will be FAIR.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

I will use my expertise and freely available information from the Internet to deliver my plan. To run the experiment, I will use free resources and run it on my computer. No fees will be required to process the plan.

